

FUNCTION Generates a prime number

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$$\text{Function1} = (3 \cdot n^2 - 4)$$

And

$$\text{Function2} = (3 \cdot n^2 - 4) / 11$$

the function can also be expressed in this cryptic form :

$$\text{Function} = (n^2 - 1 + n^2 - 1 - n^2 - 1 + n^2 - 1 + n^2) / 11 = (3 \cdot n^2 - 4) / 11$$

This function1 e Function 2 always generates many prime number.

(3*1²-4) was negative, testing absolute value.

(3*1²-4) is Unity (1)

(3*3²-4) is trivially prime!: 23

(3*5²-4) is trivially prime!: 71

(3*9²-4) is trivially prime!: 239

(3*11²-4) is trivially prime!: 359

(3*13²-4) is trivially prime!: 503

(3*17²-4) is trivially prime!: 863

(3*21²-4) is trivially prime!: 1319

(3*23²-4) is trivially prime!: 1583

(3*25²-4) is trivially prime!: 1871

(3*31²-4) is trivially prime!: 2879

(3*35²-4) is trivially prime!: 3671

(3*41²-4) is trivially prime!: 5039

(3*53²-4) is trivially prime!: 8423

(3*57²-4) is trivially prime!: 9743

(3*61²-4) is trivially prime!: 11159

(3*63²-4) is trivially prime!: 11903
(3*65²-4) is trivially prime!: 12671
(3*67²-4) is trivially prime!: 13463
(3*75²-4) is trivially prime!: 16871
(3*77²-4) is trivially prime!: 17783
(3*79²-4) is trivially prime!: 18719
(3*83²-4) is trivially prime!: 20663
(3*93²-4) is trivially prime!: 25943
(3*99²-4) is trivially prime!: 29399

From 1 to 100 (Function1) generates 24 prime numbers and divided by number 11
(Function2) generates others 19 prime numbers.

Recognized ABC Sieve file:
ABC2 File

(3*1²-4)/11 is Zero (0)
(3*2²-4)/11 is Zero (0)
(3*3²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 2
(3*7²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 13
(3*8²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 17
(3*14²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 53
(3*15²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 61
(3*22²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 131
(3*29²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 229
(3*36²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 353
(3*37²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 373
(3*43²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 503
(3*51²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 709
(3*65²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 1151
(3*66²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 1187
(3*67²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 1223
(3*73²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 1453
(3*74²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 1493
(3*81²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 1789
(3*87²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 2063
(3*88²-4)/11 is trivially prime!: 2111